

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Review of the freshwater snail *Melanoides tuberculata* (O. F. Müller, 1774) (Gastropoda, Thiaridae)

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Abstract

Melanoides tuberculata (O. F. Müller, 1774), a freshwater snail native to eastern Mediterranean, eastern Africa, southeast Asia, southern Asia, India, and Malaysia, it is an effective invader and is now nearly globally distributed. This snail has been studied with interest because of its rapidly distributed, and because of being can serve as compatible intermediate host for many of trematodes in the world.

We have summarized information from many articles in order to highlight the most important aspects of this invader snail life.

Keywords: Snail; *Melanoides tuberculata* ; Gastropoda; Thiaridae

1. Introduction

The family Thiaridae Gill, 1871(1823) is a family of freshwater snails, their members identified with turreted thick shell in varying sizes, with many moderately rounded whorls, smooth in some species and sculptured in others, and ovate aperture closed by corneous concentric or paucispiral operculum, with nearly marginal nucleus [1].

Thiarid snails were invaded most continents (South America, North America, parts of Africa) and many islands with mild climates from their original distributions [2]. Among there *Melanoides tuberculata* (O.F.Müller, 1774), a freshwater snail native to eastern Mediterranean, eastern Africa, southeast Asia, southern Asia, India, and Malaysia [3]. and invade regions outside of its natural range by human activities, particularly by the aquarium trade or the introduction of aquatic plants [4]. It has the potential to rapidly expand its population in new suitable habitats [2].

This snail presenting high inheritable phenotypic variation in the shell shape, pigmentation and sculptures [5]. *M. tuberculata* adapted to local conditions causing environmental influences producing ecophenotypic alterations [6].

The average of adults sizes within their native regions is between 20-40 mm, although some specimens as large as 80mm have been recorded [7]. Four possible factors strongly influence the growth of the shell explaining its variation among different populations: the genetic variation, the conditions of microhabitat, the chemistry of water and temperature [6].

The life span of this snail is between 2.0-3.5 years [7].

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1.1. Taxonomy

- Kingdom: Animalia
- Phylum: Mollusca
- Class: Gastropoda
- Family: Thiaridae
- Genus: *Melanoides* Olivier, 1804
- Species: *M. tuberculata* (O.F.Müller, 1774) [8].

1.2. Synonymes

- *Nerita tuberculata* O.F.Müller, 1774
- *Thiara tuberculata* (O.F.Müller, 1774)
- *Melania cancellata* Say, 1829
- *Melania layardi* Dohrn, 1858 [8].

1.3. Description

Elongate right handed shell, the length more than twice the width [9]. Rounded whorls which bearing spiral grooves and fine ridges, and bearing transverse lines that may develop into costae in older snail; groove/ridge intersections with transverse costae may give a tuberculate appearance [10]. The number of shell whorl about 8-11, featured by axial lines of rust- coloring patches [11]. The aperture of oval shape and approximately of 1/3 the length of the shell, the inner lip is slightly thickened and the outer one thin [12]. Because of the base color of the shell, this species is commonly known as "red rimmed melania" [4].

Figure 1 *M. tuberculata* (size 17-24mm) [13].

1.4. Ecology and Habitat

Inhabit aquatic environments at depths between 0.25-3.7 m [5], with salinity over of 33‰ [11]. associated with different types of substrates, macrophytes and man-made substrates, the observations showed that this snail is absent in fast current velocities streams and rivers [5] and it is restricted to waters of temperature between 18-31°C, when the water temperature exceed 35°C the snail is primarily crepuscular or nocturnal spending most of the daylight time buried in sand or mud [7].

1.5. Reproduction

M. tuberculata can reproduce by parthenogenesis [7]. The males in population extremely rare or absent [10], within their native range, some populations contain 10 to 33 % males and show the ability of sexual reproduction [7]. *M. tuberculata* become fertile when reaching 15-16 mm at the age of six months [6].

1.6. Impact on human and animal health

M.tuberculata has been reported as transmission vector and intermediate host for parasitic trematodes that affect human, wild animals and livestock [5]. The most important species are: *Clonorchis sinensis*, *Paragonimus westermani*, *Centrocestus formosanus*, *Philophthalmus gralli*, deleted name[7]. *Haplorchis pumilio*, *Haplorchis taichui*, *Acanthatrium hitaense*, *Loxogenoides bicolor*, deleted neme, *Cloacitrema philippinum*, *Cardicola alseae*, *Alaria mustelae*, *Transversotrema patialense*, *Apatemon gracilis*, *Mesostephanus appendiculatus* [6] *Echinochasmus pelecani*, *Gastrothylax crumenifer*, *Cercaria caribbea* LXVIII and *Podocotyle (Podocotyle) lepomis* [14].

M.tuberculata has competitive abilities in some habitats allowed it to be used as a biological control agent for Biomphalaria species, the intestinal Schistosomiasis intermediate hosts in many tropical regions [4]. Workers have noted declines and even extinctions of Biomphalaria, as this thiarid species has spread [15].

1.7. Ecological impacts

M. tuberculata may displace other gastropods that are found in the same geographical boundary, fortunately, it is not known to destroy aquatic plants, additionally, it is found to be good bioindicators of water quality for its ability to accumulate heavy metals in its body [16].

1.8. Distribution

M.tuberculata is an effective invader and is now nearly globally distributed except in the coldest areas [17], this snail had been described from the Coromandel coast of India in 1774 [B]. it has been detected in tropical climates all over the world [18], also invaded temperate regions wherever waters with tropical characteristics may be found [18].

M.tuberculata current distribution is Southern Asia, Indo-Pacific region, Northern Australia, Arabia, Near East, Carrebian area and much of Africa [19].

2. Conclusion

M.tuberculata is an invasive species, has successfully colonized a wide variety of aquatic habitats over a wide geographic range, many factors made the species a successful invader and ensure their rapid spread such as Parthenogenetic reproduction, the rapid growth rate. This snail serve as a vector for many parasitic trematodes that affect human and his animals.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

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